

WP2: National policy, legal and service frameworks

Psychosocial Support for Promoting Mental Health and Well-being among
Adolescent Young Carers in Europe: ME-We project, Grant Agreement number
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Country-specific report (case study) UK

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Categories	Results
<p>Specific legislation England National level</p>	<p>Children and Families Act 2014, http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2014/6/contents/enacted Targeted age group: children up to the age of 18 and families. PART 5 Welfare of children, Section 96 Young Carers Amends the Children Act 1989, https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1989/41/contents with insertions under Section 17:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Defining young carers - Placing a duty on local authorities in England to assess young carers' needs and - To identify the extent to which there are young carers within their area who have needs for support. <p>Section 17ZA Young carers' needs assessments: England (1) A local authority in England must assess whether a young carer within their area has needs for support and, if so, what those needs are, if— (a) it appears to the authority that the young carer may have needs for support, or (b) the authority receive a request from the young carer or a parent of the young carer to assess the young carer's needs for support. Definition of young carer: a person under 18 who provides or intends to provide care for another person. (12) A local authority in England must take reasonable steps to identify the extent to which there are young carers within their area who have needs for support. Targeted age group: children up to the age of 18.</p> <p>Statutory Instruments, 2015 No. 527, Children And Young Persons, England, The Young Carers (Needs Assessments) Regulations 2015, http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2015/527/made Authorities must carry out a young carer's needs assessment considering the young carer's age, the family circumstances, their wishes, needs, and preferences, and whether young carers have a difference of opinion than their parents of what they</p>

<p>want in terms of work, education, training, and opportunities.</p> <p>Targeted age group: children up to the age of 18.</p> <p>Care Act 2014, http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2014/23/contents/enacted</p> <p>An Act to make provision to reform the law relating to care and support for adults and the law relating to support for carers. It places a duty on the local authority to assess and meet the needs of a carer where care does not have to be substantial or inappropriate.</p> <p>Targeted age group: focus on transition between childhood and adulthood. There is no set age when young people reach this point; every young person and their family are different, and as such, transition assessments should take place when it is most appropriate for them.</p> <p>PART 1 Care and support, Transitions for children to adult care and support, etc., Section 63 Assessment of a young carer's needs for support</p> <p>(1) Where it appears to a local authority that a young carer is likely to have needs for support after becoming 18, the authority must, if it is satisfied that it would be of significant benefit to the young carer to do so and if the consent condition is met, assess—</p> <p>(a) whether the young carer has needs for support and, if so, what those needs are, and</p> <p>(b) whether the young carer is likely to have needs for support after becoming 18 and, if so, what those needs are likely to be.</p> <p>(2) An assessment under subsection (1) is referred to in this Part as a “young carer’s assessment”.</p> <p>Section 64 Young carer’s assessment: requirements etc.</p> <p>Sets out requirements of the ‘young carer’s assessment’</p> <p>Care and support statutory guidance (Updated 26 October 2018), Department of Health and Social Care, https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/care-act-statutory-guidance/care-and-support-statutory-guidance.</p> <p>The aim of the Statutory guidance is to support the implementation of the Care Act 2014, Care and Support (Assessment) Regulations 2014 and Support (Eligibility Criteria) Regulations 2015.</p> <p><i>Chapter 6: Assessment and eligibility</i></p>
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	<p>Whole family approach</p> <p>6.65 The intention of the whole family approach is for local authorities to take a holistic view of the person’s needs and to identify how the adult’s needs for care and support impact on family members or others in their support network.</p> <p>6.68 The local authority must also identify any children who are involved in providing care...</p> <p>6.72 Inappropriate caring responsibilities should be considered as anything which is likely to have an impact on the child’s health, wellbeing or education, or which can be considered unsuitable in light of the child’s circumstances</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Chapter 16: Transition to adult care and support</i> <p>16.6 The Care Act contains provisions to help preparation for adulthood for 3 particular groups of people - children, young carers and child’s carers.</p>
<p>Specific legislation</p> <p style="text-align: right; color: red;">Wales</p> <p>National level</p>	<p>Social Services and Well-being (Wales) Act 2014, https://www.legislation.gov.uk/anaw/2014/4/contents</p> <p>The Act provides the legal framework for improving the well-being of people who need care and support, and carers who need support, and for transforming social services in Wales. The Act gives carers a right to an assessment on the appearance of need.</p> <p>Definition of carer: a person who provides or intends to provide care for an adult or disabled child. But a person is not considered a carer if she/he provides or intends to provide care (a) under or by virtue of a contract, or (b) as voluntary work. (Section 3)</p> <p>Targeted age range: it applies to people of all ages.</p> <p>PART 3 Assessing the needs of individuals, Section 24-27 Assessing carers, especially Section 26-27 Refusal of a needs assessment for a carer aged 16, 17 or aged under 16.</p> <p>PART 4 Meeting Needs, Section 45 Power to meet support needs of a carer</p> <p>A provision for local authorities to meet the needs of carers</p>
<p>Specific legislation</p> <p style="text-align: right; color: red;">Scotland</p> <p>National level</p>	<p>Carers (Scotland) Act 2016, http://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2016/9/contents/enacted</p> <p>Definition of young carers: “young carer” means a carer who (a) is under 18 years old, or (b) has attained the age of 18 years while a pupil at a school, and has since attaining that age remained a pupil at that or another school. (Section 2)</p> <p>PART 2 Adult Carers Support Plans and Young Carers Statements, Chapter 2: Young Carer Statements, Section 12 Duty to prepare young carer statement:</p> <p>(1) In this Act a “young carer statement” means a statement prepared by a responsible authority setting out—</p>

	<p>(a) a young carer’s identified personal outcomes, (b) a young carer’s identified needs (if any), and (c) the support (if any) to be provided by the responsible local authority to a young carer to meet those needs.</p> <p>Targeted age group: under 18 or a pupil at school having attained the age of 18 while at school.</p>
<p>Specific legislation Northern Ireland National level</p>	<p>The Children (Northern Ireland) Order 1995, http://www.legislation.gov.uk/nisi/1995/755/contents</p> <p>The Children Order ensures that children’s and young people’s development is not deterred in any way. It sets out when a child is to be taken as ‘in need’.</p> <p>PART IV Support for children and their families, Section 17A Assessments and services for children who are carers, Paragraph 1:</p> <p>There is a duty on an authority to assess children and determine whether a child is to be taken to be in need if a child “the carer” provides or intends to provide a substantial amount of care on a regular basis for a person aged 18 or over or if the child requests an authority to carry out an assessment.</p>
<p>Non-specific legislation England National level</p>	<p>National Health Service Act 2006, https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2006/41</p> <p>The National Health Service Act specifically mentions carers, promoting their involvement and how services should be working together.</p> <p>Education Act 1964, http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1964/82/enacted</p> <p>All children should be entitled to their education and because of that they should have their needs considered so that they can attend school.</p>
<p>Non-specific legislation Wales National level</p>	<p>Children Act 1989, https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1989/41/contents</p> <p>PART III Support for children and families provided by local authorities in England, Provisions of services for children and their families, Wales, Section 17 Provision of services for children in need, their families and others</p> <p>(10) For the purposes of this Part a child shall be taken to be in need if—</p> <p>(a) he is unlikely to achieve or maintain, or to have the opportunity of achieving or maintaining, a reasonable standard of health or development without the provision for him of services by a local authority under this Part;</p> <p>(b) his health or development is likely to be significantly impaired, or further impaired, without the provision for him of such</p>

	<p>services; or</p> <p>(c) he is disabled</p>
<p>Non-specific legislation Scotland National level</p>	<p>Children and Young People’s Act (Scotland) 2014, https://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2014/8/contents</p> <p>An Act of the Scottish Parliament to make provision about the rights of children and young people; to make provision about investigations by the Commissioner for Children and Young People in Scotland; to make provision for and about the provision of services and support for or in relation to children and young people; to make provision for an adoption register; to make provision about children's hearings, detention in secure accommodation and consultation on certain proposals in relation to schools; and for connected purposes.</p> <p>PART 4: Provision of named persons Children and young people from birth to 18, or beyond if still in school, and their parents will have access to a Named Person to help them get the support they need. A Named Person will be a clear point of contact if a child, young person or their parents want information or advice, or if they want to talk about any worries and seek support.</p> <p>PART 5: Child's plan Ensures a single planning framework – a Child’s Plan – will be available for children who require extra support that is not generally available to address a child or young person’s needs and improve their wellbeing. Targeted age group: children up to the age of 18, or beyond if still in school, and their families.</p> <p>Education (Additional Support for Learning) (Scotland) Act 2004, https://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2004/4/contents Makes provision for the assessment of additional support needs of children and young people who could be young carers.</p>
<p>Non-specific legislation Northern Ireland National level</p>	<p>Carers and Direct Payments Act (Northern Ireland) 2002 CHAPTER 6, https://www.legislation.gov.uk/nia/2002/6</p> <p>An Act to make provision about the assessment of carers' needs; to provide for services to help carers; to provide for the making of direct payments to persons in lieu of the provision of personal social services or carers' services; and for connected purposes.</p> <p>Children's Services Co-operation Act (Northern Ireland) 2015, https://www.legislation.gov.uk/nia/2015/10/contents</p> <p>An Act to require co-operation among certain public authorities and other children’s service providers in order to contribute</p>

	<p>to the well-being of children and young persons; to require the adoption of a children and young persons strategy; and for connected purposes.</p> <p>Targeted age group: children (up to the age of 18) and young people aged between 18 and 21 years who are disabled people within the meaning of the Disability Discrimination Act 1995.</p>
<p>Enactment of legislation England & Wales National & local level</p>	<p>Care Act 2014 and Children and Families Act 2014</p> <p>Local authorities may have different approaches on how to enact the legislation. Some local areas will have fixed up local working groups to address the duties and how to implement them with a multi-agency approach. Others still have gaps between children’s services and adult services in terms of understanding what their responsibilities are under the Care Act and specifically towards young carers. The most successful areas tend to be those whose work on policies and working for young carers was pretty strong before the legislation came into place and were therefore already in a strong position to be able to implement the duties.</p>
<p>Enactment of legislation Scotland National & local level</p>	<p>Carers (Scotland) Act</p> <p>The Scottish government have an implementation steering group which meets regularly. In terms of formal evaluations there is an implementation plan for the Act.</p> <p>There is the potential to have a wide variation of the type of statement offered, because the statements were not prescribed and different local authorities have different approaches. There are also differences in the implementation of the Carers Act. Some local authorities are quite confused about who is actually in charge of this.</p> <p>Children and Young People’s Act (Scotland) 2014</p> <p>Local authorities have the duty to identify young carers and to offer them a young carers statement. If the professional who is working with the young carer feels that the young person is in need, they can refer back to the Children and Young People’s Act and under that legislation, they will have a child’s plan put in place.</p>
<p>Enactment of legislation Northern Ireland National level</p>	<p>The Children (Northern Ireland) Order 1995</p> <p>Young carers can ask for an assessment under the Children Order and if they are a child in need they can receive support.</p>
<p>Changes in legislation England & Wales</p>	<p>Children Act 1989</p> <p>Much of the Children Act 1989 applies to both England and Wales. As of April 2016, Part 3 of the Act (which refers to</p>

<p>National level</p>	<p>support for children and families provided by local authorities) has been replaced by Part 6 of the Social Services and Well-being (Wales) Act 2014.</p> <p>When it was first enacted, it did not specifically address young carers. The Act was amended by the Children and Families Act of 2014, which inserted specific provisions into the Children’s Act, (section 17ZA), which makes it a duty on local authorities in England to undertake an assessment of a young carers’ needs.</p> <p>Children and Families Act 2014 and Care Act 2014</p> <p>The Children and Families Act 2014 not only amended the Children Act 1989, but it also introduced a duty to say how many young carers there are in a local area.</p> <p>Both acts specifically mention young carers for the first time. The Children and Families Act and the Care Act made it clearer how young carers and their families should be identified, assessed and supported. In the previous legislation young carers were mentioned as a vulnerable group but it was not outlined that they had a right to an assessment of their needs.</p> <p>The changes were based on years of research, of academics working with other partners in the voluntary sector including national charities. It was a continued awareness raising about young carers’ needs, asking what needs to change.</p> <p>There were some key people within Government who helped to share messages directly from young carers about their needs. That built a picture of the whole family approach as opposed to caring for a young carer in a silo away from their family. Having those key people who were interested was important when the green papers for the Children and Families Act and Care Act were written. Consultation with young people took place over a number of years , and the right people were brought on board.</p> <p>Carers’ Assessments</p> <p>Significant changes to carers’ assessments, and to the rights of young carers and parent carers of disabled children, came into force on 1 April 2015. This is as a result of provisions in the Care Act 2014 and the Children and Families Act 2014 (England) and the Social Services and Well-being (Wales) Act 2014.</p>
<p>Changes in legislation Scotland National level</p>	<p>Carers Recognition and Services Act 1995</p> <p>In 1995 it was proposed that the Carers Recognition Act covered carers of any age. The government opposed that but eventually they conceded.</p>

	<p>Education (Additional Support for Learning) (Scotland) Act 2004</p> <p>The Education (Additional Support for Learning) (Scotland) Act 2004 (as amended 2009) places duties on local authorities to identify, meet and keep under review the needs of pupils for whom they are responsible.</p> <p>Carers (Scotland) Act 2016</p> <p>The Carers Parliament, funded by the Scottish Government, was a key element for the introduction of a legislation for carers in Scotland, because it raised the awareness toward this topic. It was kind of a natural progression, starting from a national strategy and then making it stronger, and then introducing a new legislation. In the first proposal of the Carers Act, there was nothing about young carers, because it was assumed that they are covered by the provisions within this Children and Young People’s Act. However, through consultation and the involvement of young carers, the Act was amended and now it explicitly includes young carers. Young Carer Statements were legislated for giving young carers their own provision to help ensure that they would be identified.</p> <p>Some people questioned the need for legislation specific for young carers and questioned how the Young Carers Statement would dovetail with the Child’s Plan.</p> <p>Many stakeholders were consulted including young carers who played a huge part in the development of the Act.</p>
<p>Changes in legislation Northern Ireland</p>	<p>Carers and Direct Payments Act (Northern Ireland) 2002 CHAPTER 6, https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ni/2002/6</p> <p>Amended the Children Order by inserting within it after Article 17, duties relating to assessments and services for children who are carers.</p> <p>Children's Services Co-operation Act (Northern Ireland) 2015</p> <p>Driven by the desire for better, joined up, collaborative working which is needed to solve many of the issues faced by young people.</p>
<p>Specific policy and service frameworks England National level</p>	<p>Carers Action Plan 2018 – 2020 Supporting carers today prepared by the Department of Health and Social Care, https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/carers-action-plan-2018-to-2020</p> <p>This policy paper sets out how the government will improve support for carers in England between 2018 and 2020. Chapter 3 specifically addresses young carers and their identification, improving their educational opportunities and outcomes and access to support services and the transition for young adult carers.</p> <p>Working Together to Safeguard Children - A guide to inter-agency working to safeguard and promote the welfare of</p>

	<p>children, July 2018, https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/729914/Working_Together_to_Safeguard_Children-2018.pdf</p> <p>Statutory guidance. It has a number of references to young carers (paragraphs 6; 30; 41; 46; 55; 56).</p> <p>Definition of young carer: A young carer is a person under 18 who provides or intends to provide care for another person (of any age, except generally where that care is provided for payment, pursuant to a contract or as voluntary work). (p. 105)</p>
<p>Specific policy and service frameworks</p> <p>Wales National level</p>	<p>None mentioned.</p>
<p>Specific policy and service frameworks</p> <p>Scotland National level</p>	<p>Getting it Right for Young Carers - The Young Carers Strategy for Scotland, www.gov.scot/resource/Doc/319441/0102105.pdf</p> <p>The aim is to help improve outcomes for young carers, e.g. through the identification of their needs and priorities; measures to help professionals in education, health and social care to identify young carers; etc.</p> <p>Although it refers to 2010-2015, there are still action points that the Government is keen to see fully implemented.</p> <p>Targeted age group: children or young persons aged under 18</p>
<p>Specific policy and service frameworks</p> <p>Northern Ireland Regional level</p>	<p>Children and Young People's Strategic Partnership Young Carers Group, http://www.cypsp.org/supporting-young-carers-in-schools-in-northern-ireland/</p> <p>It brings together the voluntary sector of providers working with young carers with representatives from health and social care and education to look at the needs of young carers. They have produced a booklet called "Supporting Young Carers in School" which is a co-production with the education authority.</p>
<p>Non-specific policy and service frameworks</p> <p>England National level</p>	<p>Pupil premium, https://www.gov.uk/guidance/pupil-premium-information-for-schools-and-alternative-provision-settings.</p> <p>The Pupil Premium is a pot of money that schools receive for disadvantaged pupils and that schools can use to implement additional support for their vulnerable groups of children.</p>
<p>Non-specific policy and service frameworks</p>	<p>None mentioned.</p>

Wales	
<p>Non-specific policy and service frameworks</p> <p>Scotland National level</p>	<p>Getting It Right for Every Child, https://www.gov.scot/Topics/People/Young-People/gettingitright</p> <p>It is the national approach in Scotland to improving outcomes and supporting the wellbeing of children and young people by offering the right help at the right time from the right people. It supports them and their parent(s) to work in partnership with the services that can help them. There are 8 indicators: Safe, Healthy, Achieving, Nourished, Active, Responsible, Respected, and Included.</p>
<p>Non-specific policy and service frameworks</p> <p>Northern Ireland National level</p>	<p>Children and Young People Strategy 2017-2027, https://www.education-ni.gov.uk/consultations/children-and-young-peoples-strategy-2017-2027</p> <p>The 10 year strategy includes eight parameters contributing to the well-being of children and young people. It identifies particular groups of young people who are a priority group. This includes 'children acting as carers'.</p> <p>Understanding the Needs of Children in Northern Ireland (UNOCINI) Guidance (2011) https://www.health-ni.gov.uk/publications/understanding-needs-children-northern-ireland-unocini-guidance.</p> <p>This guide is aimed at practitioners who provide services to children, young people and their families, whether they work in the statutory, voluntary, community or private sectors, which undertake or contribute to assessments under the UNOCINI Assessment Framework.</p> <p>Strategy for Supporting Families 2015-2020, http://www.northerntrust.hscni.net/pdf/NHSCT Strategy for Supporting Families.pdf</p> <p>This Strategy is an ambitious framework which is evidenced based and built upon best practice initiatives. It recognises the importance of multi-agency working and the services which focus on early intervention and prevention and the support that can be provided to parents/carers and families in their role as primary care givers.</p>
<p>Non-specific policy and service frameworks</p> <p>Northern Ireland Regional level</p>	<p>Department of Health, Families matter - Supporting families in Northern Ireland (March 2009)</p> <p>Regional family and parenting strategy, https://www.health-ni.gov.uk/publications/families-matter-supporting-families-northern-ireland</p> <p>This strategy supported the aims and objectives of the 10 year strategy 'Our Children and Young People, Our Pledge' and set out the vision for improving support and services for families and children.</p>
<p>Enactment of policy and</p>	<p>There are guidance documents, which outline and explain what the duties mean for the whole family approach for</p>

<p>service frameworks England & Wales National level</p>	<p>practitioners and about young carer’s assessments - what they include and what is good practice.</p> <p>The Care Act and Whole-Family Approaches, https://www.local.gov.uk/sites/default/files/documents/care-act-and-whole-family-6e1.pdf This document aims to provide practical guidance for practitioners working in adult social care in relation to carrying out assessments and developing plans which consider the needs of the whole family.</p> <p>No wrong doors: working together to support young carers and their families, https://www.local.gov.uk/sites/default/files/documents/no-wrong-doors-working-to-27d.pdf A template for a local memorandum of understanding between statutory Directors of Children’s and Adult Social Services – March 2015.</p> <p>A resource to help promote working together between Adult’s and Children’s social care services and enhanced partnership working with health and third sector partners. The final local text may be varied to reflect local circumstances and policies.</p>
<p>Enactment of policy and service frameworks Scotland National level</p>	<p>Getting It Right for Every Child The 8 indicators (Safe, Healthy, Achieving, Nourished, Active, Responsible, Respected, and Included) are embedded in practice to make sure every child in Scotland is supported by these outcomes. If they are not, a child’s plan is implemented.</p>
<p>Enactment of policy and service frameworks Northern Ireland National level</p>	<p>Children and Young People Strategic Partnership Young Carers Group The group includes voluntary organisations and statutory organisations that have responsibility for delivering services to children and it has a responsibility to implement and work the high level strategy for children. The partnership has to look at how the strategy will improve circumstances for young carers and it in turn has developed a working group for children in Northern Ireland. Having young carers visible within the children’s strategy means that the statutory organisations and voluntary organisations are forced to support young carers. This organisation is also responsible for the monitoring and the social service department has to report on the number of young carers.</p>
<p>Changes in policy and service frameworks England & Wales</p>	<p>None mentioned.</p>
<p>Changes in policy and</p>	<p>None mentioned.</p>

<p>service frameworks Scotland</p>	
<p>Changes in policy and service frameworks Northern Ireland National level</p>	<p>Children and Young People Strategy 2017-2027 (link see above)</p> <p>The Children’s Strategy originally was the Northern Ireland’s version of Every Child Matters (https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/every-child-matters) and it produced good outcomes for children. The Children's Services Co-operation Act 2015 requires that Northern Ireland has a Children’s Strategy and it requires that it addresses what is called the “intra-high-level parameters of well-being”. Organisations in the voluntary and statutory sector are required to work together to improve outcomes for children.</p> <p>Key stakeholders were government departments, some of the voluntary community organisations, and the Children and Young People’s Strategic Partnership.</p> <p>In the development of the Children and Young People Strategy there was some opposition since it was felt that this was not needed and that it created unnecessary bureaucracy.</p>
<p>Recognition of young carers England & Wales National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Young carers are now recognised within legislation and local authorities have to identify and assess them. Young carers are therefore recognised as a specific group who receive support and who are included within local authority policies. - In order to receive a young carer’s assessment young carers firstly need to be identified. Some children and families however do not identify with the term “young carer”, or they are frightened of having a child labelled as a young carer because that might lead to family separations.
<p>Recognition of young carers Scotland National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Young carers are recognised within legislation and local authorities have to identify and assess them. They are recognised as a specific group who receive support and who are included within local authority policies. - It is very difficult for people who have never experienced the situation of young carers, to actually conceive of the vast array of responsibilities a young child has to take on. - The main barrier is about identification
<p>Recognition of young carers Northern Ireland National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ‘Children who are carers’ are recognised in The Children (Northern Ireland) Order 1995 - The Children and Young People Strategy 2017-2027 identifies ‘children acting as carers’ as a priority group
<p>Key strengths</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Young carers are now recognised within legislation and local authorities have a duty to actively look for them and

<p>England & Wales National level</p>	<p>identify them</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Children and Families Act 2014 and the Care Act 2014 trigger a whole family approach - Comprehensive, explicit and detailed regulation for young carers - Engagement of young carers in implementing policies - Good support services: A really strong network of ‘young carer services’ which is mainly voluntary sector
<p>Key limitations England & Wales National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is a range of different definitions for the term “young carer”, which sometimes do not consider that there are children with distinct needs - Children or their families do not recognise the term “young carer”. As a consequence, they do not identify themselves as carers and they have no knowledge about their rights - The collaboration between different services does not work well due to the use of different computer systems - The implementation of a whole family approach does not work effectively because of the gaps between children’s services and adult services - There are some good practices but they are not equitably distributed across England - Young carers may not wish to come to the notice of statutory services for fear of being taken into care - Social services are stretched with limited resources. Austerity measures have impacted the capacity of local authorities - Respite activities for young carers does not prevent or reduce their caring activities - The actual support that families and young carers receive following their assessments is a bit vague
<p>Key limitations England & Wales Local level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is no template for the assessment and this creates confusion among local authorities. This results in some areas producing their own young carer’s assessment and in using different assessment tools. - The resources of local authorities for implementing the legislation, policy or service frameworks are tight - Some local authorities have massive waiting lists for assessments
<p>Key strengths Scotland National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A legal definition of the term “young carer” - With the Education (Additional Support for Learning) (Scotland) Act 2004, which was amended in 2009, young carers are recognised in schools - Minister attending the Young Carers Festival and hearing messages directly from the young people - Strong young carer voice: several forums where the young carers voice is heard nationally - The voluntary sector has a very good, easy relationship with the Scottish Government - The Scottish Government’s implement steering group for the Carers Act is a very wide group and includes representation from health and disability groups
<p>Key limitations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is a lack of awareness among the young carers themselves and knowing about their rights

<p>Scotland National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Home-schooled kids and independent schools may not be as aware of the right to an assessment as they should be - Young adult carers are not defined as a group in legislation - Child's plan went beyond the support that was needed and it was sometimes too complicated for the families - There is a wide variation of what is offered in different areas of Scotland - Capacity determines who actually gets a service - 'Manpower': Professionals might refuse to recognise a young carer if this would increase their workload - There is no national carer eligibility criteria - Carers don't always recognise themselves as carers
<p>Key strengths Northern Ireland National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Children Order 1995 creates a legislative requirement to undertake an assessment to identify children in need - The Children and Young People Strategy is a signal for organisations that young carer have to be taken into consideration
<p>Key limitations Northern Ireland National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Difficult for young carers to identify themselves in the young carer role - Lack of awareness among the society
<p>Evaluation of the current situation England National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The legislation in England is good but statutory guidance is needed - Evidence would suggest identification and assessment of the needs of young carers and families has not happened in the way it should have done. The law is not necessarily translating into practice - Adult service professionals still focus on the adult with needs and not on the child - The transition assessment brought confusion because there was not a set template for it - Governmental and political changes may have made engagement with government departments in relation to young carers more difficult <p>Definition and stigmatisation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Definition of young carer: anyone under the age of 18 years who provides or intends to provide care for another person. The words "intend to provide" highlight that prevention is also important. This means that the law can be applied not only once a young carer has reached a point of having significant need, but it should also prevent children taking on excessive and inappropriate caring responsibilities. - Young carers are not as high up on the agenda as other vulnerable children or young people. Therefore it is important to highlight their situation and remind people about the duties on a local and national level. - There is a stigmatisation of the parents of young carers because they are seen as inadequate parents due to their disabilities

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Young carers and their caring role are often presented in a negative way despite the positive elements of caring <p>Evaluation of social services</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Many social services failed previously to fulfil their legal responsibilities and now many social workers do not know that the law has changed - Social services tend to be person-specific and as a consequence, they do not look at the people around the person needing help - Young carers caring for someone with an addiction problem may not be noticed by social services because drug and alcohol misuse teams are not part of the local authority - Targets and budget cuts prevent increasing support to families - Social services are very stretched with limited resources and therefore having an assessment may not be seen as worthwhile by families - Integration between health and social care is a struggle
<p>Evaluation of the current situation</p> <p style="text-align: right; color: #C00000;">Wales</p> <p style="text-align: right;">National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The legislation is described as ineffective and as being more symbolic - The health and social care services are confused about how to deal with the legislation without enough resources - The legislation is fit for purpose but could do with a policy document
<p>Evaluation of the current situation</p> <p style="text-align: right; color: #C00000;">England & Wales</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Local level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The translation of legislation and policy frameworks into practice is mixed across the different local authorities. Sometimes there is good practice with a merger of local steering groups and young carers. But there are also gaps between children's and adult's services in terms of understanding their different responsibilities. The most successful areas tend to be those whose work on policies and working for young carers was pretty strong before the legislation came into place and were therefore already in a strong position to be able to implement the duties.
<p>Evaluation of the current situation</p> <p style="text-align: right; color: #C00000;">Scotland</p> <p style="text-align: right;">National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There are 32 local authorities so there is the potential to have 32 different types of statement - The voluntary sector has great ideas about how to change the situation but these ideas have to fit within the legislation - Social services prioritise other young people who are in their point of view in a greater need - The Carers Act is complicated and local authorities are confused about aspects of it such as who is responsible - Awareness about young carers varies across Scotland
<p>Evaluation of the current situation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is a good network of professionals and key players coming from different sectors. They share their goals for improving things for young carer together.

<p>Northern Ireland National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Beside the positive outcomes there are some worries about the transition to adult services. - Work is required to keep young carers on the agenda for adult social care - Identifying young carers is an ongoing issue
<p>Attitudes to existing policy responses UK level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Demand for numbers and quantification of the prevalence young carers from the government and a resulting dilemma between scientific integrity and the need to raise awareness among policy makers - The legislation includes guidance stating how practice should be carried out, but this does not mean that law will be necessarily translated into practice - As a consequence of the duty to identify young carers, local authorities could be picking up children with much greater needs as a consequence of very awful and difficult circumstances at home
<p>Attitudes to existing policy responses England & Wales National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive assessment of young carers' participation in forums, reviews and in making sure that the quality of services is high - Positive attitude towards whole family approach, but difficult to enact in practice - Critical view on detailed nature of central government legislation: it is hard to enact in practice because it is so detailed - Regulations explain in too much detail what that assessment should comprise - The huge level of detail in the English legislation is irrelevant - Definition of young carer: rather wide and questioned, division between ideological and pragmatic definition which produce different numbers i.e. anyone offering care (ideological) or only those seeking support (pragmatic). The government has recognised that there is not a risk of the floodgates being opened with an ideological definition, and this wider definition is welcomed by some experts. - The law is seen as useful but only if people assert their rights (young carers tend not to use the law and their parents do not know about it) - The treatment of young carers in both countries is not great and the law has not made much difference - There is a danger that the 'journey' with regards to legislation has 'come to an end' but there is still the need to ensure that legislation is implemented nationally - The legislation does not have anything about support including the need for support from young carer groups. It is thought this makes them [the groups] feel quite vulnerable and sometime vulnerable with budget cuts - Not understood why more young carers assessments are not carried out and why more action is not being taken - Interventions for disabled people is seen as more appropriate than respite for young carers
<p>Attitudes to existing policy responses</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scotland is quite far ahead in terms of awareness - Positive attitude toward having the Carers Act - Disappointment that 'young adult carers' as a group were not mentioned in the legislation (Carers Act 2016)

<p style="text-align: right;">Scotland National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Definitions need to set examples of where children are carers, because some people just do not get it. More detailed definitions are useful for professionals - Concern that young carers who decline a Statement may not get support they need e.g. from a young carers service - Expectations to produce Statements, without adequate manpower, could mean everyone will have to work a little bit harder
<p>Attitudes to existing policy responses</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Northern Ireland National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Concern about the transition to adult services
<p>Suggested changes</p> <p style="text-align: right;">England & Wales National level</p>	<p>In general</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More structural support within the education system - Early help assessments, meaning that when an ill person is referred for support there should be questions around who is providing care in order to identify young carers - Training on three levels: front line practitioners, management level and strategic director levels - To look at these children as children in need, children who are affected by parental or relative illness or disability - Appropriately evidencing the needs of young carers <p>More guidance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guidance about how to translate the legislation and policies into practice needs to be more effectively embedded and it needs to be reviewed and ensured that it is still workable for the local area - More guidance for local authorities around what an assessment should actually look like <p>More monitoring and evaluation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More national monitoring around how local authorities' duties are being implemented, ensuring that young carers have been identified and that they received a young carer's assessment - More evaluation on how the implementation of legislation and policy frameworks is working
<p>Suggested changes</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Scotland National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More efforts in raising awareness about who young carers are, so that they can be better identified and be offered support - Caution about suggesting changes before waiting to see common themes that emerge - Young carer statements should be produced for sibling carers, where this is not already happening

<p>Suggested changes Northern Ireland National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A statement on young adult carers (18-24 years old) is needed, because now there is nothing between children's services and adult's services
<p>Future goals and hopes England & Wales National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Greater international focus on young carers - To get some policy documents in England - Strengthening within legislation and policy the actual support that families and young carers should receive following their assessments - The State should be more responsive in improving the lives of the person needing care and, in turn, in improving the lives of young carers - National monitoring of the implementation of the legislation and policies and whether there are improvements for young carers and their families - A national strategy which defines what professionals should be implementing for young carers and their families - The Carers Action Plan 2018 – 2020 Supporting carers today will hopefully be a helpful instrument to embed the legislation - More support for vulnerable groups like children from parents with mental health problems or substance misuse - Reduce the stigma of those vulnerable groups - Make sure that young carers stay as a recognised subgroup of vulnerable children and do not slip off the agenda
<p>Future goals and hopes England Local level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To embed the legislation in every local area, so that there is an equitable service and access to support for families
<p>Future goals and hopes Scotland National Level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More universality and consistency across Scotland - More money that goes to the right places. More resources for funding support services - General awareness raising campaign, perhaps on television - Raised awareness of young carers about their rights - Maintaining consultation of young carers to keep their voice strong - At this stage, it is too early to change any element of the ongoing legislation. This would have an effect on many other areas
<p>Future goals and hopes Northern Ireland National Level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To continue working together with the education sector and supporting young carers in education - To develop services in terms of transition from children's services to adult services for young carers - Further work to improve how adult social care works together with the regional services to identify and respond to

	the needs of young carers
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